

A Framework for Digital Inclusion of Elderly People: DIEP

¹Tiziana Guzzo, ²Fernando Ferri, ³Patrizia Grifoni

¹, *First Author* IRPPS-CNR, tiziana.guzzo@irpps.cnr.it

² IRPPS-CNR, fernando.ferri@irpps.cnr.it

^{*3}, *Corresponding Author* IRPPS-CNR, patrizia.grifoni@irpps.cnr.it

Institute for Research on Population and Social Policies, National Research Council

Abstract

Information and communications technology (ICT) such as computers, smart phones and Internet are deeply changing and can improve the quality of life of elderly people helping them to stay independent. Many elderly people are enthusiastically learning and using these technologies. But many others encounter several difficulties with them, more precisely studying this situation as it emerges in some social centers in Italy. The aim of this paper is to: i) understand how elderly people are using ICT and what challenges they face, ii) investigate the barriers, problems and difficulties of use, and iii) identify solutions to help them using computers and other digital products. In order to reach these objectives, two different integrated methods have been used: in-depth interviews to elderly people and an open space technology (OST) to multidisciplinary experts were performed in two different steps. On the basis of the OST results, a framework was designed providing strategies and actions to involve better elderly people in using ICT.

Keywords: *Digital Inclusion, Elderly people, Information and communications technology (ICT)*

1. Introduction

The twenty-first century is characterized by two main trends: one is the rapid development of information and communication technologies (ICTs); the other is the aging of the population (mainly in the western society). Society, in fact, is facing the challenge of demographic changes. Today, society is more and more composed by elderly people. From 1980 to today, people over 60 have doubled and they will be 2 billion in 2050 OMS (2012). According to the United Nation Population Division [1], one person out of ten is now 60 or older; by 2050, one out of five will be 60 or older; and by 2150, one person out of three will be 60 or older. In Italy, there are 12 million of people older than 65, including 3,4 million of people older than 80. Elderly people are 21% of the population and in twenty years they will be 30% of the population [2]. These data confirm the steady increase in life expectancy of the population and its aging. This is a huge challenge but at the same time it represents a significant opportunity for ICT. Internet is particularly facilitating and stimulating communication and, then, the aggregation and social integration of people. Today, the biggest challenge of society is to help people not only to live longer, but also to assure them more years of health and independence. Several elderly people have lost their consort and friends, and their families live far away. These factors can cause a lack of independence and safety and lead to social isolation that can be faced stimulating and facilitating communication. Nowadays, the Governments, in conjunction with different kinds of organizations and companies, are searching new models and systems for health and social care that improve the services quality and optimize the costs.

Information and communication technologies (ICTs) run parallel to these societal changes and can play an important role in dealing with these challenges. The new ICT solutions offer good tools to maintain contacts (e.g. mobile technologies or social media), to know other people in the same condition in order to share experiences, to exchange opinions and to find moral support. [3] The social relationships with other people are important for the emotional well-being of elderly people and help to avoid social exclusion. Interaction can be carried out directly, by correspondence, by phone or by Internet.

Social Media are rapidly changing also the physician-patient relationship by allowing them to share opinions and medical information every time and everywhere. [4]

These tools play the important role to maintain and develop social relationships, even if they do not replace face to face contacts. However, they can encourage a social involvement of elderly people. Mobile technologies enable communication anywhere and anytime, allowing access to any services and creating a feeling of security and safety for elderly people and their families. Mobile phones and social media can provide information about distant relatives and they are useful tools for elderly people living far from their family. These technologies help to improve the quality of life of elderly people and give them more years of health and independence. [5] In Italy, elderly people are not using ICT so much, and they are at high risk of exclusion from the benefits of the knowledge society. How elderly people are using these technologies? What are the barriers and difficulties in using them? What are the solutions and strategies to involve better elderly people in using ICT? The paper aims at answering these questions and suggesting solutions to the Government, by carrying out in-depth interviews to elderly people and an open space technology (OST) to multidisciplinary experts.

The paper is organised as follows: in Section 2, an analysis of different studies on the use of ICT by elderly people is provided. Section 3 describes the methodology used in this study. Section 4 provides the results of the in-depth interviews to elderly people. In Section 5, the proposed Framework is introduced. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Background

Some studies found that the use of ICT by elderly people can strengthen and expand their social networks and social relationships both online and offline [6-7-8-9-10]. Cotten et al. (2012) [11] found that the use of Internet allows to decrease loneliness and to increase social contacts among elderly people in assisted and independent living communities. Moreover, the use of ICT can also reduce the geographic distance with dispersed families [12]. According to Lewis and Ariyachandra (2010) [13] social networking allows elderly people to stay in touch with their friends and family and enrich their lives. Therefore, the acceptance and utilisation of these technologies by the elderly people is becoming increasingly important [14]. However, different studies claimed that there are some barriers related with the use of ICT by elderly people, which are related to physical and cognitive changes. Some obstacles are the reduction of visual acuity and the precision of eye-movement control that don't allow distinguishing text and buttons [15]. The use of computers by elderly people is also complicated because they cannot see what is on the screen [16]. Other problems are related to the difficulty to learn and the short term memory on new subjects, along with limited financial means [17]. Difficulties related to motor control in using the mouse and the lack of experience were underlined by Williamson et al (1997) [18].

According to Hernández-Encuentra (2009) [19] the adoption of ICT by elderly people is not only a problem of usability, but other aspects such as attitudes, experience of use, and perceived benefits must also be taken into account.

Amaro and Gil (2011) [20] conclude that elderly people should be part of the process of shaping technology/ICT according to their interpretations of how to use technology. ICT, in fact, do not have one single meaning for elderly people, but can be interpreted in different ways by different elderly people groups.

Xie et al. (2012) [21] carried out an exploratory study to analyse elderly people's perceptions of social media and the educational strategies to facilitate their learning. Privacy was the main concern and barrier that has been found. Effective educational strategies, based on introducing the concepts before introducing the functions, answering to privacy concerns, and making social media personally relevant, changed the elderly perceptions from strong negative to more positive but cautious.

Lewis and Ariyachandra (2010) [13] introduced some key factors that influence elderly people to use social networks, such us: privacy, security, trust, desire to give and get information, web experience, social norms, enjoyment, gender and computer anxiety. In his opinion, elderly people will surf more online in the future when new applications will be developed.

According to the review by Nef (2013) [22] the main benefit of using social networks by elderly people is to have an intergenerational communication with younger generations for the benefit of both generations. According to him, the main barriers are privacy concerns, technical difficulties and the fact that the needs of elderly people are not taken into account by Web design. Choi and DiNitto (2013) [23] found that social capital facilitated learning and adoption of Internet while depression and anxiety symptoms, were negatively associated with Internet use.

Guilliani et al. (2005) [24] have shown that innovative technologies are accepted by users if usefulness and perceived benefits are high. The studies of McCreddie et al. (2005) [25] and Sanchez et al. (2005) [26] affirmed that beyond need satisfaction, reliability is another very important aspect in the perception and consequently in the acceptance of these technologies.

Charness and Boot (2009) [27] claimed that an obstacle to accept new technologies is their inadequate design. In fact, they should be designed keeping in mind the abilities and the changes caused by the ageing of elderly people. Another obstacle is guidebooks that are often written in a difficult language to understand [28].

In [29] the way to “better design and right use of ICT in today’s ultra-modern virtual worlds” is analysed, underlining the importance of involving both professionals as well as common users in ICT tools development.

Starting from these studies, the paper aims at analysing how ICT are used by elderly people in Italy, identifying the advantages and weakness of their adoption and how it is possible to overcome the constraints that limit their use.

3. Methodology

Two qualitative methodologies were carried out in two different steps: in-depth interviews to elderly people and an open space technology (OST) to interdisciplinary experts (ICT teachers, geriatricians, social operators, software engineers and sociologists).

In the first step, face to face, open, deep interviews to elderly people were carried out. Sixteen elderly people from different backgrounds were chosen. The elderly people interviewed are part of two different groups (one that uses ICT and one that does not use them). 9 elderly people came from the “University of Third Age (UTE) of Rieti” in the Lazio Region and 7 came from a senior center “Casale Ciribelli” in Rome.

A semi-structured interview guide was defined with the following objectives: (1) to understand the knowledge and experience of elderly people on computer and Internet; (2) to individuate the issues related to the benefits, limits and challenges of the use of digital technologies; (3) to identify the best ways to involve elderly people in using ICT. These objectives were addressed by the following required information and guiding questions:

- *Gender*
- *Age*
- *Level of education*
- *Occupation*
- *How is your knowledge on the computer/Internet?*
- *Do you use them?*
- *On average, for how long per day/week/month?*
- *For which reasons do you mainly use them?*
- *What are the characteristics or features that your computers or mobile phones should have to push you to use them more?*
- *What are instead the issues that push you not to use them?*
- *What are the possible advantages of using computers/Internet?*
- *What are the possible disadvantages or problems using computers/Internet?*
- *How important are for you the opinions or suggestions of others people in using them?*
- *Typically, do you suggest other people to use them?*
- *Do you use Internet?*
- *How much time do you spend on Internet? For which reasons?*
- *What do you dislike about Internet?*
- *Do you think that the use of Internet is risky? For which reasons?*
- *Do you use mobile phones to get connected on Internet?*
- *Do you join some social networks? Why do you use them?*

- *Do you know what they are?*
- *Do you think that they are useful? For which reasons?*
- *Do you like / would like to use them?*
- *Why do you not use them?*
- *Would you use them if....*
- *Have you ever used Internet for medical purposes? (search for information about illnesses, seek opinions online, seek moral support, etc.).*
- *For what in particular?*
- *What do you think about these services?*
- *How useful are these sites?*
- *Are they easy to use?*
- *What are your concerns when browsing these sites?*
- *How should these sites be for you to use them?*

Each participant was given information on key issues and guiding questions.

As the interviews were open, the interviewed people had the possibility to expand or add other comments to the asked questions. Besides the defined questions, elderly people were welcome to freely describe their experiences in dealing with computers, mobile phones and any other ICT tools. The interviews proceeded from January to March 2014. By interviewing people from different backgrounds (i.e. different level of education, different level of knowledge and experiences of ICTs), a diversified set of opinions on their issues were collected.

On the basis of the interviews outcome, in a second step, an open space technology (OST) with experts was carried out. A selection of the main open questions that had resulted from the interviews were shared among the experts who were participating in the OST. During this meeting, the issues and problems that have emerged were discussed in order to find shared solutions. The aim of the OST is to allow participants to define short reports in a reasonable time, each one presenting proposals on how to face the open questions emerged from the interviews, as well as the other experts critical contributions.

Ten experts (coming from different relevant disciplines to examine and identify the key challenges and the existing gaps) were chosen, each one having a particular view or knowledge on the matter. A briefing-paper encouraged individual preparation in advance. The OST aimed at discussing about the constraints that limit the use of ICT among elderly people and to provide solutions to overcome them.

The open space technology involved the following steps:

- Preparation: all the participants were arranged in a circle and the facilitator welcomed them;
- Setting the agenda: the facilitator discussed the theme of the meeting;
- Discussion sessions: participant collaboratively discussed aspects and issues of the theme;
- Results: all of the most important ideas were identified, explored, addressed and summarised in a report.

4. Results of in-depth interviews

Sixteen elderly people have been interviewed, which included seven males and nine females, aged between 62 and 81 years and with a medium-high level of education. Their knowledge and experience with ICT is medium-low.

Some respondents began to use a computer already during their working age, but their activities were related to specific tasks, which were always repetitive. The use of the PC was limited only for few activities. Other respondents, with the advent of the computer at their work place, have had a rejection of the new technology, as evident in the following comment:

“When the computers have been developed at work, I was one of the best of the old technique and I would be one of the worst of the new technique. So I resigned and went into retirement. I immediately got a refusal for new technologies”.

Some interviewed people who have attended computer courses, said that they had never used a computer before the courses; they did not even know how to turn it on. Elderly people are approaching the use of computers because of curiosity and because sometimes they are pushed by their family members. *“I’m not very familiar with computers, I took a course under the influence of my brother”.*

Sometimes a real generational challenge with their grandchildren is created. *“My grandchildren ask me to play with them on the computer, but they are more talented than me. I would like to learn (to be able to use computer) to keep up with them”*.

But the greater stimulus to begin the use of PC is given by the everyday life. Indeed interviewed people said that they use computers mainly to manage their house, for example to make online payments of bills, bank account and also for personal interest, curiosity, to seek information and not to feel cut off. *“The activities that I primarily perform are related to: insurance, bank account, bus routes, read newspapers, medical information, recipes, play cards and see photos”*. A senior who does not use Internet said: *“If I would have Internet, I would use it... to search information, recipes, read newspapers and look for references on doctors”*.

The greatest part of activities carried out are related to search information of each kind, to communicate with relatives and friends, and to organize activities for the free time, as stated in the following sentences which gives some opinions provided by the interviewed people: *“On YouTube, there are some interesting videos on rose pruning...”*. *“With Google Earth I can see distant places that I saw when I was young and, I can see how these places have changed during the years...”*.

More specifically, sharing photos and videos with relatives and friends seems to be the most relevant motivation that drives elderly people to use computer: *“Transferring camera images on the PC and then on a DVD was the first thing that pushed me to approach computers...”*. *“It is less than one year that I am using the computer. I like to do researches on the history, on disorders and I like watching videos. But the most amazing and beautiful thing to do, in my opinion, is to see photos of distant family, to and keep in touch with them using video calling”*.

Among the advantages of the ICTs, elderly people highlighted the possibility to carry out some tasks directly from home and in real time (home banking, be in touch in real time with family and friends by using videoconferencing). *“In my opinion, the main advantages of Internet are: to be informed, to work easily, to find people you have not heard for years...”*. *“In the past, every time you made a mistake when writing a letter or a document with an old typewriter, you had to toss the paper and start over. Now everything is more automated and simple...”*.

Among the disadvantages of the emerging ICTs, the risk of addiction is deeply perceived by the interviewed people. Elderly people are afraid to spend too much time in front of their PC, and consequently to postpone other things. The biggest risk according to them is to become isolated, not to go for a walk anymore and meet people, losing the human relationships. *“I fear of being isolated, staying at home alone with the computer. People must moderately use computers”*.

The interviewed people said that the time they usually spend on the computer is an average of 1-2 hours per day. It seems that they are ashamed to say that they spend a lot of time on the computer. They are concerned about the risk of danger of addiction, mainly in using Internet. The risks and problems on the use of Internet were also identified. More specifically they identified the risks connected with problems related to hacking, viruses and especially privacy. *“On Internet, inaccurate and sometimes false information is given. Moreover, you can know everything of a person. With Facebook for example, sometimes you fall into banality, unnecessary comments”*. *“I have a few friends on Facebook, just people I know. It is dangerous to have many contacts if you do not know them de visu. I like to comment on the radio that I listen to, upload photos that I like to share with others, post comments on current”*. Internet seems to be useful as a tool that can improve already existing relationships; elderly people seem to appreciate the ICTs opportunities when the virtual improves relationships and services of real life.

With respect to e-commerce, elderly people do not trust online purchases, they prefer the direct contact and personal relationship with the seller, and they fear possible scams. Some of them do not like it because they prefer to see the products before buying anything. *“On the Net you may meet many dishonest people. For people who are unfamiliar with the computer it is easier to be cheated”*. *“I’m afraid to buy on Internet, I have no trust in giving my personal information and credit card”*.

Some difficulties of access are also related to interaction and the digital divide. Elderly people would like to interact more easily with computers. Due to their problems related to memory and sight, they would like larger types and a more immediate way to search information. *“It is stressful for me to use computers and ICT tools, because it is not so natural for me to use them. I have some problems with my memory and I cannot remember all the steps”*.

With respect to social networks, although elderly people are appreciating certain qualities of these tools, such as finding people they did not hear for years, or sharing medical problems and learning how

other people solve problems, they do a little use of social networks, as they prefer face to face contacts. Besides a literacy problem, it is a cultural issue. Elderly people are tied to a well defined mindset, and few are inclined to changes. They have a fixed pattern of thinking and acting, they use a difficult approach. *“We elderly people have some difficulty to access computers, we need to understand how to use it! But sometimes we are afraid to fail so we do not even enroll in courses, because of our fear of losing face”*. There is a technological barrier. Sometimes elderly people are afraid to keep going when they encounter a problem.

“I’m afraid to block the computer, or to touch some wrong button and then break it...”. “There should be simpler instructions, more immediate steps. If you accidentally make a mistake, the computer can block. (One time, to repair it, I paid 50 euro)”.

Sometimes it is also a matter of money, since not all people can afford a computer or an Internet connection. *“For those of us who have a low retirement pension, the costs of courses and ADSL connection are a problem”*. In order to address this problem, elderly people would like Institutions to supply free of charge courses. *“I would propose that Municipalities provide young people to teach courses to elderly people and they should be set out on useful things and daily practice not on theory”*. Some interviewed people have expressed the desire to have a physical helpdesk at their disposal to solve small problems of interaction with the computer. The greatest difficulty is that they feel left to their own devices. Other interviewed people underlined the importance to have at disposal some PC shared in public spaces where it can be used jointly with other people, producing a contamination in the ability in the use and avoiding the isolation, reducing the digital divide with building a collective knowledge and reinforcing the trust in the use of the PC and Internet.

5. Building the DIEP Framework

From the analysis of the interviews to elderly people, four main elements that influence the digital inclusion were evident:

- *Accessibility;*
- *Motivations;*
- *Trust;*
- *Usability.*

Figure 1. The elements of the process of elderly people digital inclusion

On the basis of these outcomes, an open space technology (OST) with ten experts was carried out.

They discussed on these issues and gave some proposals to face the open questions.

According to the experts, with respect to the *“access”*, there are three initial barriers: sight, hearing and hands. Elderly people have some problems because they do not clearly see what is written on the monitor, they may not hear the teacher’s explanations and can have problems using the mouse. Another issue is the difficulty to remember passwords. Also touch screens are a problem because when they broaden it, they lose the orientation.

Some of the issues that elderly people encounter in using technology rise from the fact that standard products do not take their specific needs into account. These difficulties can be avoided through the development of the products. Graphical user interfaces seemingly so simple can become a major obstacle for those who cannot see the mouse cursor move on the screen. Many people with vision

problems can be excluded from potentially useful sites because of an inappropriate design. Those with reduced physical mobility, such as paralysis or various forms of arthritis, may experience difficulties in moving the mouse or using a keyboard. People with problems of hearing or deaf people have difficulties using network videos, or hearing the warning sounds of the computer. There are still deficiencies in software designs and contents of Web sites which do not take these issues into account. New technical solutions that consider the physical and cognitive limitations of elderly people are necessary.

Considering the “*motivations*”, it is firstly necessary to overcome some barriers to encourage elderly people towards what is new and strange and to introduce a facilitated approach of the codes in such a way that they come in daily practice. Therefore, increasing the level of acceptance of such technologies is crucial. Elderly people have a difficulty of approach: for example grandmothers with the advent of washing machines. There is the need to teach them the difference between remembering and knowing how to do things. They have to understand the mechanisms and not to memorize them. There is the need of a basic computer, that is closer to the language of every day. For example, English messages terrify them. It is important both to teach them how to use the computer and to give them strong motivations to use it. The perceived benefits should be higher in order to push elderly people to use computers. It is important to teach them the possibility to simply access public administration online, to give them tools to save time and money buying online securely without risks for them, to find social relationships and moral support in social networks.

Elderly people are using computer mainly for fun and practical use. The experience and cultural context of each count for much if they have distant relatives, they want to learn to use Skype to communicate with them. Generally, women are more motivated, and are multi-tasking.

The “*usability*” is fundamental for overcoming digital divide, producing a wide and aware use of ICTs. New technologies can improve the quality of life of elderly people only if they are developed according to criteria that allow everyone to use them. Therefore, technologies should be simpler and easier to use, in line with the actual and concrete users’ needs. The common aim should be to make ICT usable for all people and to satisfy users’ expectations. To support this strategy, interfaces should be user-friendly, multi-modal, context-aware, intelligent, and interactive, simplifying the human-computer interaction. A multimodal system is a hardware/software system that enables the reception, interpretation, processing input and generating output of two or more interactive modes in an integrated and coordinated way.

Multimodal interaction is a good solution to improve the efficiency of ICT for elderly people, because it offers improved flexibility, usability and interaction efficiency, allowing the user to interact through input modalities, such as speech, handwriting, hand gesture and gaze, and to receive information from the system through output modalities, such as speech synthesis, smart graphics and others modalities, opportunely combined.

With respect to “*trust*”, one of the main concern of elderly people is that the posted information online, such as their photos, e-mail addresses or personal information can be accessed by people they do not know that can potentially make a bad use of it, e.g. sending spam e-mails and viruses. The other concern is about fraud in e-commerce sites, and fear to use credit card. Privacy, unknown people and personal information seem to be three key factors of trust for elderly people.

To improve the issues related to trust, elderly people must be given the right tools. They sometime do not have tools to address the issue of privacy, and it is necessary to teach them how to defend themselves. In Italy, more publicity should refer to the possibilities related to these issues.

Today, the challenge of our aging society is to make ICT solutions easier to use and accessible to elderly people to enable them to be socially active, to enjoy a healthier and higher quality of daily life for longer and to maintain a high degree of independence, autonomy and dignity. To reach these objectives it is firstly necessary to enhance usability, improve accessibility, give motivations and increase trust.

Starting from these considerations given by experts, the DIEP framework has been designed.

The figure 2 illustrates the DIEP Framework with the main actions and strategies to reach the main objective to enhance the digital inclusion of elderly people.

Figure 2. The DIEP Framework

The actions that should be put in place to facilitate the access to new technologies and overcome social exclusion by elderly people are to:

- Provide technical solutions and provide more appropriate design responding the specific needs of elderly people;
- Take into account the changes of elderly people's physical and visual abilities by encouraging the design and production of computer technology;
- Give training courses, establish a computer literacy program addressed to elderly people who are far from using information technology, and provide tools to address the issue of the privacy to increase trust in ICT;
- Promote a regional program for the development and diffusion of new technologies to increase the autonomy and freedom of people;
- Promote through incentives and trade agreements, a spread of computers even in families who are not in possession and / or renewal of technologies;
- Provide user-friendly interfaces for an easy interaction and use a multimodal communication using different modalities of interaction with the computer, enhancing usability;
- Give a social and economic advantage online for example to buy products and services at lower costs, to access the public administration online, to make elderly people feel less alone;
- Promote the need for a cultural mediation in all dissemination activities and learning new technologies.

6. Conclusion

New technologies have important and positive socio-economic impacts and represent an opportunity for social inclusion and autonomy. To learn how to use information technology means, especially for elderly people, to extend the duration and the quality of their autonomy.

The main problem that elderly people have in using technologies is the difficulty to acquire skills with new tools as their short-term memory is reduced. In fact, they express the need to have more natural and easy-to-use technologies at their disposal, in order to be able to improve their independence. Moreover, they wish technologies would assure more security and independence.

The study described in this paper has been carried out in Italy, where the population aging and the need to overcome digital divide are two factors characterizing society.

Interviewed people expressed some concerns about the privacy, although many of them do not have a great perception of potential dangers online.

The majority of interviewee people underlined that the everyday usefulness is the key factor that encourage in the use of ICTs. In fact courses can be very useful for having some preliminary notions in the use of PC, but also curiosity and helps in daily activities encourage their use.

The frequent use can create the necessary knowledge of ICT tools and increase their acceptance. For this purpose a collective use of PCs and Internet can produce a contamination and the necessary exchange of knowledge. They need more knowledge and tools to address this issue.

Another important aspect that emerged from the interviews was that some interfaces do not take into account of the functional limitations of ageing such as: loss of vision or tactile sense, hearing impairment, memory or balance loss, difficulty in using a computer mouse or small buttons. They expressed the need of training sessions for elderly people that are low skilled with technologies.

Elderly people perceived these technologies as tools that can improve their life. They are favorably disposed to accept these technologies as a support in their daily life, but some concerns are perceived in a negative way. In order to increase the acceptance of these technologies by users, it is fundamental (for designers) to take into account the issues discussed in this paper and make devices that are user-friendly, not intrusive, reliable and low-cost.

An aspect, emphasized by elderly people, was the issue about the lack of usability of some devices. As elderly people can have the necessity to use different modalities of interaction according to their disabilities, multimodal interfaces could provide a helpful support. The multimodal communication in fact not only allows accessing information anytime and anywhere, but also to communicate the same information to the user in more than one form (visual, voice, gestures, touch) at the same time, with the aim to help overcoming difficulties related to cognitive disabilities, sensory and physical properties.

Multimodal applications should be able to adapt to changes in device capabilities, user preferences and environmental conditions. Multimodality can improve accessibility to services and information, to users with visual impairments or difficulty in recognizing colors, such as using an additional voice to the visual that provides additional output vowels.

7. References

- [1] United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs/Population Division World Population Prospects: The 2012 Revision, Key Findings and Advance Tables, 2013.
- [2] ISTAT, Relazione Istat sullo stato sanitario del Paese 2009-2010. Ministero della Salute - Direzione Generale del Sistema Informativo e Statistico Sanitario, 2010.
- [3] Guzzo, T., D'Andrea, A., Ferri, F., Grifoni, P., Social Media: The Evolution of E-health Services. In: Gündüz-Ogüdücü, Sule, Etaner-Uyar, A. Şima. (Eds) Social Network Analysis: Tutorials and Case Studies. Springer Lecture Notes in Social Networks series, 2014.
- [4] D'Andrea, A, Ferri, F., Grifoni, P., Guzzo, T., "Multimodal Social Networking for Healthcare Professionals". In proceedings of the Workshops on Database and Expert systems applications DEXA 2010, Bilbao, Spain, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 147-153, 2010.
- [5] D'Ulizia, A, Ferri, F., Grifoni, P., Guzzo, T., Smart Home to support elderly people: Innovative Technologies and Social Impacts. In: Coronato A., De Pietro G. (Eds) Pervasive and Smart Technologies for Healthcare: Ubiquitous Methodologies and Tools. IGI Global, pp. 25-38, 2010.
- [6] Gatto, S.L., Tak, S.H., "Computer, Internet, and Email Use Among Older Adults: Benefits and Barriers", Educational Gerontology, (Taylor & Francis Group), vol. 34, pp. 800-811, 2008.
- [7] Hogeboom, D.L., McDermott, R.J., Perrin, K.M., Osman, H., & Bell-Ellison, B.A., "Internet Use and Social Networking among Middle Aged and Older Adults", Educational Gerontology, (Taylor & Francis Group), vol. 36, pp. 93-111, 2010.
- [8] Morris, A., Goodman, J., & Brading, H., "Internet Use and Non-Use: Views of Older Users", Universal Access in the Information Society, vol. 6, pp. 43-57, 2007.
- [9] Nimrod, G., "Seniors' Online Communities: A Qualitative Content Analysis", The Gerontologist, vol. 50, no.3, pp. 382-392, 2009.
- [10] Sum, S., Matthews, M.R., Pourghasem, M., & Hughes, I., "Internet Technology and Social Capital: How the Internet Affects Seniors' Social Capital and Well-being", Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication, vol. 14, pp. 202-220, 2008.
- [11] Cotton, S.R., Anderson, W., McCullough, B., "The impact of ICT use on loneliness and contact with others among older adults". Gerontechnology, vol. 11, no.2, p. 161, 2012.

- [12] Winstead, V., Anderson, W.A., Yost, E.A., Cotten, S.R., Warr, A., & Berkowsky, R.W., "You Can Teach an Old Dog New Tricks: A Qualitative Analysis of How Residents of Senior Living Communities May Use the Web to Overcome Spatial and Social Barriers", *Journal of Applied Gerontology*, 2012.
- [13] Lewis, S., Ariyachandra, T., "Seniors and online social network use". *CONISAR Proceedings* vol. 3 no. 1522, 2010.
- [14] Broady, T, Chan, A, Caputi, P., "Comparison of older and younger adults' attitudes towards and abilities with computers: Implications for training and learning". *British Journal of Educational Technology*, vol. 41, no.3, pp. 473-485, 2010.
- [15] Czaja, L., Design computer systems for older adults. In: Jacko JA, Sears A (Eds) *The Human-computer-interaction handbook*. Lawrence Erlbaum, Mahwah, pp. 413-427, 2003.
- [16] Echt, K., Designing web-based health information for older adults: visual considerations and design directives. In Morrell RW (Ed) *Older adults, health information and the World Wide Web*. Lawrence Erlbaum, pp. 61-87, 2002.
- [17] Steyaert, S., "Towards the Desired Future of the Elderly and ICT: Policy recommendations based on a dialogue with senior citizens". *Proceedings of the Seminar on Future-Oriented Technology Analysis: Impact of FTA Approaches on Policy and Decision-Making*. Seville, 2006.
- [18] Williamson, K., Bow, A., Wale, K.,, "Breaking down the barriers to public Internet access". *Proceedings of the International Conference of Computer Communication and International Telecommunications Society*, Calgary, pp. 234-256, 1997.
- [19] Hernández-Encuentra, E., Pousada, M., Gómez-Zúñiga, B., "ICT and Older People: Beyond Usability", *Educational Gerontology*, (Taylor & Francis Group), vol. 35 no. 3, pp. 226-245, 2009.
- [20] Amaro, F., Gil, H., "ICT for Elderly People: «Yes, 'They' Can!» 2011 e-CASE & e-Tech" *International Conference January 18-20, 2011, Toshi Center Hotel, Tokyo, Japan, 2011*.
- [21] Xie, B., Watkins, I., Golbeck, J., Huang, M., "Understanding and Changing Older Adults' Perceptions and Learning of Social Media". *Educational Gerontology*, Taylor & Francis Group, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 282-296, 2012.
- [22] Nef, T., Ganea, R. L., Müri R. M., Mosimann U. P., "Social networking sites and older users – a systematic review". *International Psychogeriatrics*, 2013.
- [23] Choi, N. G., DiNitto, D. M., "Internet Use Among Older Adults: Association With Health Needs, Psychological Capital, and Social Capital", *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 2013.
- [24] Guillian, V., Scopeletti, M., Fornara, F, "Elderly People at Home: Technological Help in Everyday Activities". *IEEE, International Workshop on Robots and Human Interactive Communication*, http://www.dinf.ne.jp/doc/english/Us_Eu/conf/csun_99/session0260.html, 2005.
- [25] McCreddie, C., Tinker, A, "The Acceptability of Assistive Technology to Older People". *Aging & Society*, vol. 25, pp. 91-110, 2005.
- [26] Sanchez, J., Calcaterra, G., Tran, Q.Q., "Automation in the Home: The Development of an Appropriate System representation and its effects on reliance", In *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society 49th Annual Meeting (HFES'05)*, Santa Monica: Human Factors and Ergonomics Society, 2005.
- [27] Charness, N., and Boot, W.R., "Aging and Information Technology Use: Potential and Barriers. Current Directions" *Psychological Science*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 253-258, 2009.
- [28] Hawthorn, D., "Interface design and engagement with older people". *Behaviour & Information Technology*, vol. 26, no.4, pp. 333-341, 2007.
- [29] Feng, J., Li, J., Hughes, J., "When Two Ends Meet: Professionals and Users of ICT", *JNIT: Journal of Next Generation Information Technology*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 48-56, 2014.